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The Avoidable Mortality in the Italian Regions

It decreased by an average of 28% in the Italian regions between 2006 and 2018

Istat-BES calculates the value of avoidable mortality in the Italian regions. Avoidable mortality consists of the deaths of people aged between 0 and 74 whose cause of death is considered treatable or rather deaths that could have been avoided thanks to health care, prevention, and health treatments or that it would have been preventable with primary prevention interventions. The index is based on a base of 10,000 inhabitants.

Ranking of the Italian regions for avoidable mortality in 2018. Campania is in first place for the value of avoidable mortality with an amount in 2018 equal to 20.9, followed by Sicily with a value of 18.8 units and Molise with an equal value to 17.9 units. In the middle of the table there are the Aosta Valley with an amount of avoidable mortality in 2018 equal to an amount of 17.2, followed by Friuli-Venezia Giulia with an amount equal to 17.00 and by Liguria with 16.9 units. Umbria and the Marches close the ranking with a value of 14.8 units and Trentino-Alto Adige with an amount of 14.1 units. On average in 2018 in the Italian regions there were 17 avoidable deaths per 10,000 inhabitants.

Ranking of countries by percentage change in preventable deaths between 2006 and 2018. Liguria is in first place in terms of the percentage change in preventable deaths between 2006 and 2018 with an amount equal to -22.48% equal to a reduction of -4.90 units, followed by Abruzzo with a reduction of -22.58% equal to an amount of -4.90 and by Molise with a variation of -24.15% equal to an amount of -5.70 unit. And in the middle of the table there are Lazio with an amount equal to -26.86% equal to an amount of -6.50 units, followed by Campania with a variation of -27.43% equal to a value of -7.90 units, and from Tuscany with an amount of -27.96% equal to an amount of -5.90 units. Lombardy closes the ranking with a variation of -33.19% equal to an amount of 7.80 units, followed by Trentino-Alto Adige with a value of -35.62% equal to an amount of -7.80 units, and from Valle d'Aosta with a variation of -40.07% equal to a variation of -11.50 units. Overall, on average, avoidable deaths in the Italian regions decreased between 2008 and 2016, the value of avoidable deaths decreased by an amount of -28.56% equal to an amount of -6.70 units.

Italian Macro-Regions. The value of avoidable deaths has decreased both in the North and in the Center and in the South of Italy. Between 2006 and 2018 the value of avoidable deaths decreased from an amount of 23 to a value of 15.9 or equal to a variation of -7.1 units equal to a variation of -30.86%. Between 2006 and 2018 the value of avoidable deaths decreased in Central Italy from an amount of 22.4 units to a value of -16.3 units or equal to a variation of -6.1 units equal to a variation of -27.23%. In the South the value of avoidable deaths decreased from an amount of 25 units up to an amount of 18.5 units or equal to a variation of -6.5 units equal to a variation of -26.00%.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm: Silhouette Vs Elbow. A clustering model with k-Means algorithm is analyzed below. To optimize the k-Means algorithm, a comparison between the Silhouette coefficient method and the Elbow method is presented. With reference to the use of the Silhouette coefficient, it is possible to identify two clusters indicated below, namely:

- Cluster 1: Sicily, Lazio, Sardinia, Valle d'Aosta, Calabria, Campania, Piedmont, Friuli-Venezia Giulia, Basilicata;

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- Cluster 2: Tuscany, Emilia-Romagna, Veneto, Umbria, Trentino-Alto Adige, Marche, Puglia, Liguria, Lombardy, Abruzzo, Molise.

It is therefore possible to analyze the value of the medians of clusters 1 and 2 and it follows that the median value of avoidable deaths of cluster 1 is equal to an amount of 17.5 units, followed by cluster 2 with a value of 15.3 . The following order therefore derives from it, that is: $C1 = 17.5 > C2 = 15.3$. From the point of view of geographical analysis, the contrast between the eastern regions which have a lower value of avoidable mortality compared to the western regions which have a higher avoidable mortality value is evident.

A clustering model was then created with the Elbow method that relates the number of K to the value of SSq. Through the use of the Elbow method it is therefore possible to identify a number of clusters equal to 3.

It is therefore possible to recalculate the optimal number of clusters considering $k = 3$, resulting in the following clustering achieved with k-Means, that is:

- Cluster 1: Sardinia, Lazio, Calabria, Piedmont, Aosta Valley, Sicily, Friuli-Venezia Giulia, Basilicata, Molise, Abruzzo;
- Cluster 2: Tuscany, Veneto, Emilia-Romagna, Umbria, Trentino-Alto Adige, Marche, Puglia, Lombardy, Liguria;
- Cluster 3: Campania.

However, by comparing the clusterization with the k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient compared with the clusterization carried out with the k-Means algorithm optimized with the Elbow method it is possible to verify that in the transition between a clusterization with $k = 2$ ad a clustering with $k = 3$ does not significantly increase the explanatory capacity of the model. In fact, the only real difference between the model made with the Silhouette coefficient and the model made with the Elbow method consists in the fact that in the model suggested by the Elbow method there is a third cluster which, however, has only one element, namely the Campania, which is a leader in terms of avoidable deaths.

Network Analysis. An analysis carried out with network analysis is presented below. Network analysis is achieved through Euclidean distance. The following characteristic elements of network analysis are therefore indicated, namely:

- Number of nodes: 20;
- Number of edges: 40;
- Average degree: 4;
- Density: 0.2105.

Four different types of reticular structures are therefore found, of which two are complex and two are of the bi-univocal type.

- A first complex structure that is detected brings together the following regions, namely: Emilia-Romagna, Tuscany, Veneto, Umbria, Trentino-Alto Adige. The following relationships arise:
- Emilia-Romagna is connected to Tuscany with a link having a value of 0.81, and to Veneto with a link having a value of 0.92;
- Tuscany is connected to Emilia Romagna with a link having a value of 0.81, to Veneto with a link having a value of 0.73, and to Umbria with a link having a value of 0.77;

- Veneto is connected to Emilia Romagna with a value of 0.92, to Tuscany with a value of 0.73 units and to Trentino-Alto Adige with a value of 0.71 units;
- Trentino-Alto Adige is connected to Veneto with a link with a value of 0.71 units;
- Umbria is connected to Tuscany with a value of 0.77 units.

A second complex network structure is made up of three different regions, namely Sardinia, Calabria and Lazio. Particularly:

- Lazio is connected to Sardinia with a link having a value of 0.51 units, and to Calabria with a link having a value of 0.76;
- Sardinia is connected to Lazio with a link with a value of 0.51 and to Calabria with a value of 0.87;
- Calabria is connected to Lazio with a link with a value of 0.76 and to Sardinia with a link with a value of 0.87.

To these complex reticular structures must be added two simple two-way link structures indicated below, namely:

- Two-way connection between Liguria and Puglia with a link value of 0.67;
- Two-way connection between Friuli-Venezia Giulia and Piedmont with a link having a value of 0.88.

It must be considered that the cluster structure does not in any way indicate the presence of causal relationships but rather the presence of a set of similar dynamics between the data structures.

Machine Learning and Predictions. Eight different machine learning algorithms were applied below for the prediction of the preventable mortality value in the Italian regions. The algorithms were trained with 70% of the available data while the remaining 30% was used for the actual prediction. The performance of the algorithms was analyzed based on the ability to maximize R-squared and minimize the following statistical errors, namely: "Mean Absolute Error", "Mean Squared Error", "Root Mean Squared Error". The following ordering of the algorithms by predictive capacity is therefore carried out below, that is:

- PNN-Probabilistic Neural Network with a payoff value of 4;
- Random Forest Regression with a payoff value of 8;
- Tree Ensemble Regression with a payoff value of 13;
- Gradient Boosted Tree with a payoff value of 15;
- Simple Regression Tree with a payoff value of 20;
- ANN-Artificial Neural Network with a payoff value of 25;
- Polynomial Regression with a payoff value of 27;
- Linear Regression with a payoff value of 32.

Therefore, by applying the best performing algorithm or the PNN-Probabilistic Neural Network, it is possible to predict the following variations in the avoidable mortality index for the indicated regions, namely:

- Friuli-Venezia Giulia with an increase from an amount of 17.00 up to a value of 17.5 or a change of 0.5 units equal to an amount of 2.9;
- Emilia-Romagna with an increase from an amount of 15.3 up to a value of 15.7 units or equal to a value of 0.4 units equal to a value of 2.6%;
- Marche with an increase from an amount of 14.8 units up to a value of 15.2 units or equal to an absolute change of 0.4 units equivalent to a value of 2.7%;

- Lazio with an increase from an amount of 17.7 units up to a value of 17.4 units or equal to a variation of -0.3 units equal to an amount of -1.69%;
- Molise with a decrease from an amount of 17.9 units up to a change of 17.5 units or equal to a variation of -0.4 units equal to an amount of 2.23%;
- Puglia with an increase from an amount of 16.5 units up to a value of 16.9 units or equal to a variation of 0.4 units equal to a variation of 2.42%;

Therefore, the application of the best performing algorithm predicts an increase in avoidable mortality of an amount equal to 0.16 units or 1.00% on average for the regions analyzed.

Conclusions. The analysis of avoidable mortality certainly shows a positive trend from a temporal point of view. In fact, in the historical series presented, avoidable mortality is reduced practically in all Italian regions in the period between 2006 and 2018. However, there are still significant territorial divergences even if in this case it is not possible to find the pattern of the contrast. North South. In fact, there are some southern regions that perform well in terms of reducing avoidable mortality such as, for example, Puglia and Abruzzo. On the contrary, there are some regions of the North that have high levels in terms of avoidable mortality, such as Piedmont for example. However, it is also true that most of the regions that have high levels of avoidable mortality are southern regions such as Campania, Calabria, Sicily. Furthermore, it must be considered that the analyzed data stops at 2018. And most likely the value of avoidable mortality has significantly increased during the covid 19 pandemic.

Reference

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Appendix

Clusterizzazione per Mortalità Evitabile in Italia ne 2021.

Regioni	2018	Prediction	Var Ass	Var Per
<i>Friuli Venezia Giulia</i>	17,00	17,50	0,50	2,94
<i>Emilia Romagna</i>	15,30	15,70	0,40	2,61
<i>Marche</i>	14,80	15,20	0,40	2,70
<i>Lazio</i>	17,70	17,40	-0,30	-1,69
<i>Molise</i>	17,90	17,50	-0,40	-2,23
<i>Puglia</i>	16,50	16,90	0,40	2,42
<i>Media</i>	16,53	16,70	0,17	1,01

Algorithms	R^2	mean absolute error	mean squared error	root mean squared error	Totale
<i>PNN</i>	1	1	1	1	4
<i>Random Forest Regression</i>	2	2	2	2	8
<i>Tree Ensemble Regression</i>	3	4	3	3	13
<i>Gradient Boosted Tree Regression</i>	4	3	4	4	15
<i>Simple Regression Tree Learner</i>	5	5	5	5	20
<i>ANN</i>	6	7	6	6	25
<i>Polynomial Regression</i>	7	6	7	7	27
<i>Linear Regression</i>	8	8	8	8	32

Algorithm	R ²	mean absolute error	mean squared error	root mean squared error
ANN	-0,36198318	0,298419841	0,154812614	0,393462341
PNN	0,850233292	0,093034128	0,020710022	0,143909771
Simple Regression Tree Learner	0,28796721	0,188461538	0,079164201	0,281361336
Gradient Boosted Tree Regression	0,458610035	0,156907443	0,056541141	0,237783812
Random Forest Regression	0,798730486	0,131803259	0,023035192	0,151773489
Tree Ensemble Regression	0,460404626	0,176259787	0,064611181	0,254187296
Linear Regression	-2,8677	0,521505376	0,366805411	0,605644624
Polynomial Regression	-0,59469394	0,260683761	0,182226605	0,426880083

Ranking dei paesi per variazione percentuale delle Morti Evitabili tra il 2006 ed il 2018

Rank	Regioni	Var Ass	Var Per	Rank	Regioni	Var Ass	Var Per
1	Liguria	-4,90	-22,48	12	Toscana	-5,90	-27,96
2	Abruzzo	-4,90	-22,58	13	Sardegna	-7,10	-28,98
3	Molise	-5,70	-24,15	14	Emilia-Romagna	-6,50	-29,82
4	Calabria	-5,90	-24,89	15	Veneto	-6,70	-30,73
5	Sicilia	-6,30	-25,10	16	Friuli-Venezia Giulia	-7,60	-30,89
6	Marche	-5,10	-25,63	17	Umbria	-7,10	-32,42
7	Puglia	-5,80	-26,01	18	Lombardia	-7,80	-33,19
8	Basilicata	-6,20	-26,16	19	Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol	-7,80	-35,62
9	Lazio	-6,50	-26,86	20	Valle d'Aosta/Vallée d'Aoste	-11,50	-40,07
10	Campania	-7,90	-27,43	21	Media	-6,70	-28,56

Ranking delle regioni per mortalità evitabile nel 2018

Rank	Regione	2018	Rank	Regione	2018
1	Campania	20,9	11	Liguria	16,9
2	Sicilia	18,8	12	Abruzzo	16,8
3	Molise	17,9	13	Puglia	16,5
4	Calabria	17,8	14	Lombardia	15,7
5	Lazio	17,7	15	Emilia-Romagna	15,3
6	Piemonte	17,5	16	Toscana	15,2
7	Basilicata	17,5	17	Veneto	15,1
8	Sardegna	17,4	18	Umbria	14,8
9	Valle d'Aosta/Vallée d'Aoste	17,2	18	Marche	14,8
10	Friuli-Venezia Giulia	17	19	Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol	14,1